

Production and Characterization of Cellulose Nanofibers from Cow Dung Waste

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Abstract:

Today, the use of synthetic polymers had been increased and this could produce adverse effects on the environment. So there is an emerging need to produce materials from natural polymers like cellulose. In this study, we produce nanocellulose in ecofriendly method for sustainable development of the environment. We focus on the conversion of excretory wastes into valuable nanocellulose. Cow dung- the abundant waste source of animal husbandry is utilized as the raw material for the production of cellulose nanofibers. Present study produces cellulose nanofibers through the following steps such as alkaline pretreatment, bleaching and 60% sulphuric acid hydrolysis. The produced nanocellulose shows the presence of cellulose peak in FTIR analysis and the crystallinity index of nanocellulose was found to be 56.8% via XRD results. The structural morphology and elemental composition of the raw material, cellulose and nanocellulose fibrils was observed through SEM-EDX. Zeta potential value of the nanocellulose was found to be -15.6mV. Thermal stability and Differential Thermal Analysis of the nanocellulose was determined through Thermogravimetric analysis.

Key words: Cow dung, Nanocellulose, Alkaline treatment, Bleaching, Acid Hydrolysis.

Introduction:

The advancement in Nanocellulose(NC) has gained huge impact in recent years and attracts researcher's interest due to its specific features such as simpler production methods, morphological variations, and facile surface modification. Nanocellulose possess certain outstanding features such as high mechanical properties, biodegradability, biocompatibility, and renewability. The presence of free hydroxyl (OH) on its surface permits easy modifications by way of distinct chemical and physical techniques to appreciate it with precise useful properties. Novel materials and composites using nanocellulose had been advanced via the researchers for diverse applications such as packages in food industry, in biomedical substances and devices, cosmetics, paper and pulp industries, regenerative drug treatments, stabilizing agent in dispersion, petrochemical factories, environmental remediation, application in electronics devices and so forth (Huang *et al.*, 2019). Celluloses with tiny particle size which is greater than or equal to 100 nm is called nanocellulose. Nanocellulose, the unique and valuable product made from natural cellulose source and produced by some microbial and cell-free systems (Ullah *et al.*, 2021). In recent times, the application of green, renewable and sustainable substances has become increasingly more essential for producing various high-cost products with low environmental issues (Oksman *et al.*, 2016). Synthetic polymers and petroleum based materials release negative environmental impacts. There is an urgent need to replace the plastics and synthetic polymers which are non-biodegradable (Sumesh *et al.*, 2020). This can be exclusively replaced by natural polymers. Among them, cellulose is the most abundant naturally available and renewable compound, A God's gift from the biosphere which is present in plants, algae, tunicates, and a few bacteria (Vazquez *et al.*, 2015).

Many researchers focused on the production of nanocellulose from agricultural residues and their conversion into novel materials. Whereas, herbivore manure is the less explored, more and easily available resource which contains abundant cellulose polymers. Herbivores such as cow, sheep, goat, horse, elephant and so on feed on plant based foods which contains and excrete wastes which contain celluloses and other plant based polymers. In this research, we focus on cow dung to produce Cellulose Nanofibres(CNFs).

Figure 1: Lignocellulosic composition of cow dung (Puri *et al.*, 2020)

The celluloses are built by β -1,4-D-glucose units, a homopolysaccharide sugars. It consist of both amorphous and crystalline domains. The major steps to be followed during the production of nanocellulose are as follows. The first and foremost step is the pretreatment of lignocellulosic biomass (LCB). The complex structures of LCB constitutes of Cellulose, Hemicellulose and Lignin that are held together in nature. Inorder to isolate the cellulose polymers, it is important to break and remove the lignin and hemicellulose structures which could be effectively performed by pretreatment methods. Different types of pretreatment are physical (various milling treatment, thermal treatment, microwave pretreatment and ultrasound pretreatment), physicochemical (steam explosion and plasma pretreatment), chemical (alkaline hydrolysis, acid hydrolysis, organo solvents, ionic liquids, Deep Eutectic Solvents and so on) and Biological methods. (Orlando *et al.*, 2020 and Mankar *et al.*, 2021). The second step is bleaching which removes the color of the sample and whitens it. Bleaching also removes the partial lignin content present in it. Finally nanocellulose is produced from cellulose using several methods such as high pressure homogenization, acid hydrolysis, TEMPO oxidation method and so on which results in production of nanosized crystalline cellulose.

The main objective of the current study is to investigate the characteristics of the produced cellulose nanofibers such as its structural morphology, presence of cellulose, removal of lignin and hemicellulose, crystallinity index of the material after each progressing steps such as alkaline extraction, bleaching and acid hydrolysis. In this study, colloidal stability of produced nanocellulose in aqueous suspension and the thermal stability and decomposition of the nanocellulose were also investigated carefully.

Materials and methods:

The cow dung was collected from the local farms of the Tirupur District, Tamil Nadu. The collected raw materials were cleaned well to get rid of insects, stones and sands present in it. Then it was washed thoroughly in distilled water until the pH becomes neutral. Then samples were allowed to dry in Hot Air Oven at 70°C for several hours until the cow dung fibres dried completely without any moistures. The fibres were then grounded into fine powders and it was sieved. The cow dung powders were kept in hot air oven at 60°C for 45 minutes to avoid microbial contamination in the samples. The samples were labelled as Raw Material- Cow Dung (RM-CD).

Alkaline extraction:

The samples were subjected to Alkaline treatment with 4 wt% NaOH solution for 1 hour under 100°C with intermittent stirring. The solid is to liquid ratio was maintained as 1:10. The obtained pulp was washed with distilled water. The process were repeated for 4 times. Finally, the alkaline treated pulp was collected and washed thoroughly in distilled water until pH reaches 7.

Bleaching:

The alkaline treated samples were subjected to bleaching. Equal volumes of hydrogen peroxide and glacial acetic acid was used for bleaching with 1:10 solid is to liquid ratio. Bleaching was done for 6 hours under 80°C. The dried cellulose pulp were then obtained by washing the pulp several times till it becomes neutral and then dried in hot air oven. Thus obtained dried cellulose after bleaching were labelled as Bleached Cellulosic Pulps (BL-CP)

Acid Hydrolysis:

BL-CP was stirred using distilled water in magnetic stirrer to made it slurry and it was subjected to acid hydrolysis with 60% sulphuric acid under 45°C for 1 hour. 10-fold of chilled distilled water was added to quench the acid hydrolysis reaction. The suspensions were washed thoroughly several times by centrifuging using distilled water at 12000 rpm. The suspensions were dialyzed with distilled water until the pH reaches 7. Obtained nanocellulose was sonicated for 10 minutes to produce homogenized nanocellulose. Then the sample was lyophilized and labelled as Acid Hydrolyzed Nanocellulose (AH-NC). The produced nanocellulose were used for further characterizations.

Characterization of Nanocellulose:

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR):

FTIR analysis for the sample AH-NC (nanocellulose) was done in Shimadzu's FTIR instrument. The transmittance were recorded from the wavenumber 400cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹ by performing 45 scans in the resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

X Ray Diffraction (XRD):

XRD were performed for the samples RM-CD, BL-CP and AH-NC using XPERT-PRO Diffractometer system. The continuous scanning was done using Cu as anode material at 45 kV and 30mA. The start position $2\theta=10$ from where the diffraction intensities were started to record and end at $2\theta = 80$.

Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (Fe-SEM):

The microstructural morphology of the samples RM-CD, BL-CP and AH-NC were visualized using MIRA3 TESCAN's high resolution FE-SEM with an accelerating voltage of 10 kV.

Zeta potential (ZP):

Zeta potential of the sample AH-NC was analysed to identify the surface charge of the produced nanocellulose. The aqueous suspension with concentration of AH-NC as 0.2g/100 ml was prepared to identify zeta potential value using Zetasizer Ver. 7.13 9 (Malvern Instruments Ltd).

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA):

TGA was performed to determine the Percentage of weight loss and Differential Thermal Analysis of produced nanocellulose. Approximately 5 mg of sample was used to identify the thermal stability of the isolated nanocellulose. TGA for the sample AH-NC was performed using Mettler Toledo TGA2 analyzer. Weight loss pattern of the sample were recorded from room temperature to 600°C under nitrogen atmosphere at a heat rate of 10°C/min.

Result and Discussion:**Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR):**

Figure 2: FTIR Analysis of AH-NC

The acid hydrolyzed nanocellulose were analyzed by FTIR to identify the chemical and functional groups. From the obtained FTIR spectrum, the two main domains of absorption were predicted: the low- wave number domain from 500 to 1650 cm^{-1} and the high wave number domain from 2000 to 3350 cm^{-1} . No peak was observed between the wave number 1510 and 1600 cm^{-1} confirms the absence of lignin in the produced nanocellulose (Puri *et al.*,2020). No peak formation was seen around the wave number 1730 cm^{-1} which indicates the complete removal of hemicellulose from the sample (Zheng *et al.*,2019 and Xu *et al.*, 2018). From this identification, we can confirm that hemicelluloses were completely degraded during the process of NaOH treatment. The absorbance in the region 895.80 determines the presence of β - glycosidic bonds in cellulose, the band determines the deformation of $\text{C}_1\text{-H}$ in celluloses. The peak found at 1158.51 cm^{-1} is related to C-O-C stretching vibrations in pyranose ring. The peak at 1642 cm^{-1} corresponds to H-O-H stretching of celluloses that are attributed to the bending of water molecules that are absorbed in the sample. Any absorption between 3000 to 3500 cm^{-1} determines the vibrational stretch of free O-H groups present in the cellulose (Pavalaydon *et al.*, 2021). The wavebands present at 3337.54 cm^{-1} and 2884 cm^{-1} corresponds to the stretching of OH group and C-H bonds respectively in the cellulose structures. (Puri *et al.*,2020, Zheng *et al.*,2019 and Trilokesh *et al.*, 2019).

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD):

The x ray diffraction studies were performed for three different samples RM-CD, BL-CP, AH-NC. Crystallinity % of each sample was calculated using the formula: Area of crystalline peaks/Area of all peaks *100. The crystallinity index of the raw material, bleached cellulose and nanocellulose was found to be 23.1%, 29.1% and 56.8% respectively. From the obtained result, it is known that the crystallinity index of the sample is changed after each treatment. The gradual increase in crystallinity of the nanocellulose can be seen here which is due to the presence of high of crystalline structure and the damage of amorphous structures during acid hydrolysis.

Figure 3: 3D Stacked graph of XRD

Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (Fe-SEM) with Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX):

The morphology of the produced nanocellulose was visualized using SEM. The difference in morphology of the image is observed at each step. In fig 4.A), we can observe a complex structures of lignocellulosic biomass in raw powdered cow dung. In fig 4.B), the broad tube shaped fibers of cellulose with lack of complex structures are visualized. This was due to NaOH and bleaching treatment which could remove the lignin and hemicelluloses. From the obtained sem results in fig 4.C), we can conclude that a long tube like nanofibers are produced from the cowdung. Also the image shows aggregated cellulose nanofibers which could affect the stability of nanofibers. This statement coincides with the zetapotential results of the nanofibers.

Figure 4 : A). SEM image of RM-CD. B). SEM image ofBL-CP. C) SEM image of AH-NC.

Figure 5: A). Area taken for EDX analysis of RM-CD. B). Area taken for EDX analysis of B—CP. C). Area taken for EDX analysis of AH-NC.

Figure 6: A). Elemental composition analysis of RM-CD. B). Elemental composition analysis of BL-CP. C). Elemental composition analysis of AH-NC

Sample RM-CD			Sample BL-CP			Sample AH-NC		
Element	Weight %	Atomic %	Element	Weight %	Atomic %	Element	Weight %	Atomic %
C K	45.38	55.05	C K	42.34	49.45	C K	42.41	49.52
O K	43.39	39.52	O K	57.66	50.55	O K	57.59	50.48
Mg K	1.40	0.84						
Si K	5.68	2.95						
P K	1.23	0.58						
Ca K	2.93	1.07						

Table 1: Percentage of Elements in different samples

Zeta Potential (ZP):

The produced nanocellulose was characterized by zetapotential to identify the stability of suspensions in aqueous medium. After sulphuric acid hydrolysis, the nanocellulose was stabilized by sulphate groups that are introduced during acid hydrolysis. The anionic sulphates present on the surface of the nanocellulose was responsible for negative zeta potential value. In this study, the nanocellulose hydrolyzed with inorganic sulphuric acid was found to have a zeta potential value of -15.6 mV which indicates the stability of AH-NC in aqueous suspension is not much good as it forms aggregation.

Figure 7: Zeta potential graph of AH-NC

S.No	source	Type of nanocellulose	H ₂ SO ₄ Concentration	Crystallinity index	Zeta potential value	Reference
01	Tea stalk	Cellulose nanocrystals	Optimized H ₂ SO ₄ concentration: 62.20% at 1:15 Solid: liquid ratio	61.32%	-33.39	Guo <i>et al.</i> , 2020
02	Jack fruit peel	Cellulose nanocrystals	65% H ₂ SO ₄ at 1:9 Solid: liquid ratio	83.42%	-11.6 mv	Trilokesh <i>et al.</i> , 2019
03	Ground nut shell	Cellulose nanocrystals	65wt % H ₂ SO ₄ at 1:20 Solid: liquid ratio	74%	-22.5mV	Bano <i>et al.</i> , 2017
04	Cow dung	Cellulose nanofibers	65% H ₂ SO ₄ at 1:10 Solid: liquid ratio	53.30%	- 37.53 mV	Puri <i>et al.</i> , 2020
05	Pine apple peel	Needle shaped cellulose fibres	64% (w/w) H ₂ SO ₄ at 1:20 Solid: liquid ratio	61.19%	- 36.7	Dai <i>et al.</i> , 2018
06	Cow dung	Cellulose nanofibers	60% H₂SO₄ at 1:10 Solid: liquid ratio	56.8%	-15.6 mV	This study

Table 2: A literature review on nanocellulose produced via sulphuric acid hydrolysis

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA):

Thermal stability of the isolated nanocellulose was determined using TGA. Three stages of thermal degradation in the form of weight loss were observed. At the initial temperature of 27.4 °C the percentage of weight of the nanocellulose was found to be 100%. The first step of thermal degradation in which small weight loss of 8.26% was due to evaporation of water and other volatile molecules present in the sample. Nanocellulose starts to decompose approximately at a temperature between 200-300 where the slight mass loss happens and significantly leads to the second step of degradation. Major weight loss of 71.78% happened in second step of degradation, i.e., between 250 to 380 is due to the pyrolysis of cellulose. This step significantly indicates the thermal stability of the polymer. The decrease in thermal stability is due to the reduced crystallinity and the introduction of number of sulfate groups during sulphuric acid hydrolysis. In third stage of degradation, a steady state weight loss of 6.19% is due to degradation of carbon residues that are left over. At the final temperature 597.5°C the percentage of weight of nanocellulose was found to be 13.2%.

Figure 8: Curves depicting the weight loss of AH-NC during TG analysis

Figure 9: DTA curves of AH-NC

Conclusion:

In this current study, nanocellulose was isolated from the cow excretory waste. The cellulose composition present in cow dung depends upon the cow feed. Here, nanocellulose was produced through series of steps such as alkaline treatment, bleaching and acid hydrolysis. Characterization such as FTIR, XRD, Fe-SEM with EDX, Zeta Potential and TGA were performed to understand the characteristics of produced nanocellulose. The results of the study demonstrated the absence of hemicellulose and lignin and presence of cellulose polymers in the form of nanofibers after sulphuric acid hydrolysis. Nanocellulose produced in this method was found to have low stability due to aggregation. Therefore, enhanced acid hydrolysis with high acid concentration and enhanced ultrasonic treatment is recommended to produce nanofibers with high stability.

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